

The Isotopic Abundance Ratio of Consciousness Energy Treated L-Tryptophan Using LC-MS Spectrometry

Keywords: L-tryptophan; Biofield Energy; The Trivedi Effect®; Consciousness Energy Treatment; Isotopic abundance

Abstract

L-tryptophan is an essential amino acid, essential for normal growth of child and adults, protein synthesis, precursor of serotonin, melatonin, and niacin. The research work was designed to investigate the impact of the Trivedi Effect®-Consciousness Energy Treatment on the structural properties and the isotopic abundance ratio of L-tryptophan using liquid chromatography – mass spectrometry analytical technique. The L-tryptophan sample was divided into Control and the Biofield Energy Treated tryptophan. The treated tryptophan sample received Biofield Energy Treatment (the Trivedi Effect®) remotely for ~3 minutes by Mr. Mahendra Kumar Trivedi, who was located in the USA, while the test samples were located in the research laboratory in India. The mass spectra of both the tryptophan samples at retention time 2 minutes exhibited the molecular ion mass peak adduct with hydrogen ion at m/z 205 ($C_{11}H_{13}N_2O_2^+$) along with low molecular fragmented mass peaks at m/z 188 and 102 for $C_{11}H_{12}N_2O_2^+$ and $C_8H_6^+$, respectively. The isotopic abundance ratio of P_{m+1}/P_m ($^2H/^1H$ or $^{13}C/^12C$ or $^{15}N/^14N$ or $^{17}O/^16O$) in the Treated L-tryptophan was significantly increased by 21.89% compared with the Control sample. Therefore, ^{13}C , 2H , ^{15}N , and ^{17}O contributions from $C_{11}H_{13}N_2O_2^+$ to m/z 206.08 in the Treated tryptophan was increased significantly compared to the Control sample. The change in the isotopic abundance might be due to the modification in nuclei possibly through the interference of neutrino particles with the help of the Trivedi Effect®-Consciousness Energy Treatment. The increased isotopic abundance ratio of the Treated tryptophan may increase the intra-atomic bond strength, increase its stability, and shelf-life. The Biofield Energy Treated tryptophan might have increased the stability and shelf-life compared to the Control sample. The Treated tryptophan would be more stable in the nutraceutical, and pharmaceutical formulations, which would be advantageous for the prevention and treatment of pellagra, depression, kynurenine. It could also maintain the normal label of tryptophan and avoid increase of its metabolite, lower the neurotoxin and a metabotoxin behavior, glutaric aciduria type I disorder, eosinophilia-myalgia syndrome, etc. The Treated L-tryptophan would be advantageous for the improvement of yield, productivity, and quality of crops and other plants.

Introduction

L-tryptophan is an essential amino acid, necessary for normal growth of child and adults, protein synthesis, precursor of serotonin, melatonin, and niacin. It is also the precursor of indole alkaloids and auxin plant hormone [1,2]. It increases the production of serotonin in the body [1,3]. It is obtained from the foods and supplements. Food sources of tryptophan are red meat, eggs, fish, poultry, brown rice, soybeans, oats, dried dates, milk, chocolate, yogurt, cottage cheese, sesame, peanuts, pumpkin seeds, chickpeas, almonds, sunflower seeds, spirulina, etc. [1,2]. Hartnup's disease, improper diet, high maize diets, fructose malabsorption, etc. are the main cause for the reduced levels of tryptophan in the body. Tryptophan deficiency may cause

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pellagra; the other deficiency diseases are depression and kynurenine. If the label of tryptophan and its metabolite increase, it can behave like a neurotoxin and a metabotoxin, eosinophilia-myalgia syndrome, glutaric aciduria type I disorder, create an incurable and sometimes fatal flu-like neurological condition, etc. [1, 2, 5-8]. L-tryptophan is slightly soluble in water, very slightly soluble in alcohol, practically insoluble in ether and chloroform. Heat decompose it and emits toxic fumes of nitric oxide [1].

Physicochemical properties of L-tryptophan are very important for the pharmaceutical and nutraceutical formulations and other industrial applications [9]. The Trivedi Effect®-Consciousness Energy Treatment have the amazing capabilities to transform the properties of many living and non-living object(s) [10-14]. The Trivedi Effect® is a natural and only scientifically proven phenomenon in which an expert can harness this inherently intelligent energy from the Universe and transmit it anywhere on the planet through the possible mediation of neutrinos [15]. Every living organism possesses a unique infinite, para-dimensional electromagnetic energy field surrounding the body known as the Biofield Energy. The Biofield Energy Healers can harness the energy from the "Universal Energy Field" and can transmit into any living or non-living object(s), which is known as the Biofield Energy Treatment. There are several Biofield based Energy Therapies that are used nowadays against various disease conditions [16-18]. The Biofield Energy therapy has been recognized worldwide as a Complementary and Alternative Medicine health care approach by National Center of Complementary and Integrative Health with other therapies, medicines and practices such as traditional Ayurveda, Chinese herbs and medicines, naturopathy, homeopathy, yoga, meditation, Qi Gong, Tai Chi, acupressure, acupuncture, healing touch, Reiki, hypnotherapy, cranial sacral therapy, etc. [19]. Such therapies have been well accepted by most of the U.S.A. population with advantages [20]. The Trivedi Effect®-Consciousness Energy Treatment also reported with significant results altering the intrinsic properties of metals, organic compounds, ceramics, polymers, microbes, and cancer cell line; improved yield, productivity, and quality of crops, improved bioavailability of pharmaceutical and nutraceutical compounds, and altered the isotopic abundance ratio

Figure 1: Liquid chromatograms of the Control and the Biofield Energy Treated L-tryptophan.

[21-31].

Study of the natural stable isotope ratio analysis has many applications in the different field to understand the isotope effects resulting from the alterations of the isotopic composition [32-34]. Gas chromatography – mass spectrometry (GC-MS) and liquid chromatography – mass spectrometry (LC-MS), are the widely used sophisticated analytical techniques for the analysis of isotope ratio with sufficient precision [33]. The Consciousness Energy Treatment could be an economical approach to obtain a better desirable L-tryptophan with improved physicochemical properties for the supplements, nutraceutical, and pharmaceutical formulations. Therefore, this study was designed and evaluated the impact of the Trivedi Effect on L-tryptophan using LC-MS for the structural characterization and the isotopic abundance ratio of P_{M+1}/P_M ($^2H/^1H$ or $^{13}C/^{12}C$ or $^{15}N/^{14}N$ or $^{17}O/^{16}O$) compared to the Control sample.

Materials and Methods

Chemicals and Reagents

L-tryptophan (> 99%) was purchased from Alfa Aesar, India and other chemicals used in the experiment were of analytical grade purchased in India too.

Consciousness Energy Treatment Strategies

The test compound L-tryptophan was divided into two parts, among which, one part did not receive the Biofield Energy Treatment and considered as the Control sample. The second part of the test compound received the Energy of Consciousness Treatment remotely for ~3 minutes through the Unique Energy Transmission process by Mr. Mahendra Kumar Trivedi, who was located in the USA, while the test samples were located in the research laboratory in India, and it was labelled as the Biofield Energy Treated L-tryptophan. On the other hand, the Control sample was subjected to “sham” healer, who did not have any knowledge about the Biofield Energy Treatment, under the similar laboratory conditions. After that, the Biofield Energy Treated and un-treated L-tryptophan samples were kept in sealed conditions and characterized using LC-MS analytical technique.

Characterization

Liquid Chromatography-Mass Spectrometry (LC-MS) Analysis and Calculation of Isotopic Abundance Ratio

The liquid chromatography-mass spectrometric analysis of the Control and the Biofield Energy Treated L-tryptophan was carried out with the help of LC-MS Thermo Fisher Scientific, the USA equipped with an ion trap detector connected with a triple-stage quadrupole mass spectrometer. The column used here was a reversed phase Thermo Scientific Synchronis C18 (Length-250 mm X ID 4.6 mm X 5 micron), maintained at 25°C. The diluent used for the sample preparation was methanol. The L-tryptophan solution injection volume was 10 µL and the analyte was eluted using acetonitrile (80%) + 0.1% formic acid (20%) pumped at a constant flow rate of 1 mL/min. Chromatographic separation was achieved using gradient condition and the total run time was 10 min. Peaks were monitored at 278 nm using the PDA detector. Mass spectrometric analysis was performed under ESI +ve ion mode. The total ion chromatogram, peak area% and mass spectrum of the individual peak which was appeared in LC along with the full scan (m/z 50-400) were recorded. The total ion chromatogram and mass spectrum of the individual peak (appeared in LC-MS) were recorded.

The natural abundance of each isotope (C, H, N, and O) can be predicted from the comparison of the height of the isotope peak with respect to the base peak. The values of the natural isotopic abundance of the common elements are obtained from the literature [35-37]. The LC-MS based isotopic abundance ratio (P_{M+1}/P_M) for the Control and the Biofield Energy Treated L-tryptophan ($C_{11}H_{13}N_2O_2^+$) was calculated.

$$\text{Percentage (\%)} \text{ change in isotopic abundance ratio} = [(IAR_{\text{Treated}} - IAR_{\text{Control}}) / IAR_{\text{Control}}] \times 100$$

Where IAR_{Treated} = isotopic abundance ratio in the Treated sample and IAR_{Control} = isotopic abundance ratio in the Control sample.

Results and Discussion

Liquid Chromatography-Mass Spectrometry (LC-MS)

Both the samples of L-tryptophan showed a single prominent peak at retention time (R_t) of 2.1 minutes in the LC-MS chromatograms (Figure 1). This result indicated that both the samples are pure and have similar polarity.

Figure 2: Mass spectra of the Control and the Biofield Energy Treated L-tryptophan at R_t 2.1 minutes.

Table 1: LC-MS based isotopic abundance analysis results in the Biofield Energy Treated L-tryptophan compared to the Control sample.

Parameter	Control sample	Biofield Energy Treated sample
P_M at m/z 205 (%)	100.00	100.00
P_{M+1} at m/z 206 (%)	10.60	12.92
P_{M+1}/P_M	0.11	0.13
% Change of isotopic abundance ratio (P_{M+1}/P_M) with respect to the Control sample		21.89

The mass spectra of both the samples of L-tryptophan are presented in Figure 2. The mass spectra of both the samples at R_t of 2 minutes exhibited the presence of the molecular ion of L-tryptophan adduct with hydrogen ion at m/z 205.08 (calcd for $C_{11}H_{13}N_2O_2^+$, 205.1), along with low molecular fragmented mass peaks at m/z 188 and 102 for $C_{11}H_{12}N_2O_2^+$ and $C_8H_6^+$, respectively (Figures 3). The fragmentation pattern of the experimental data was well supported by the published literature data [38]. The study confirmed the structure of the sample as L-tryptophan.

Isotopic Abundance Ratio Analysis

The Control and the Biofield Energy Treated samples showed the molecular ion mass peak at m/z 205.08 (calcd for $C_{11}H_{13}N_2O_2^+$, 205.1) with 100% relative abundance in the spectra. The theoretical calculation of isotopic peak P_{M+1} for the protonated L-tryptophan presented as below:

$$P(^{13}C) = [(11 \times 1.1\%) \times 100\% \text{ (the actual size of the } M^+ \text{ peak)}] / 100\% = 12.1\%$$

$$P(^2H) = [(13 \times 0.015\%) \times 100\%] / 100\% = 0.195\%$$

$$P(^{15}N) = [(2 \times 0.4\%) \times 100\%] / 100\% = 0.8\%$$

$$P(^{17}O) = [(2 \times 0.04\%) \times 100\%] / 100\% = 0.08\%$$

P_{M+1} i.e. ^{13}C , 2H , ^{15}N , and ^{17}O contributions from $C_{11}H_{13}N_2O_2^+$ to m/z 206.08 = 13.18%

The calculated isotopic abundance of P_{M+1} value 13.18% was close to the experimental values (Table 1). From the above calculation, it has been found that ^{13}C and ^{15}N have the major contribution to m/z 206.

The LC-MS based isotopic abundance ratio analysis P_M and P_{M+1} for L-tryptophan near m/z 205 and 206, respectively of the Control and the Biofield Energy Treated samples, which were obtained from the observed relative peak intensities of $[M^+]$ and $[(M+1)^+]$ peaks,

respectively in the mass spectra (Table 1). The isotopic abundance ratio of P_{M+1}/P_M ($^2H/^1H$ or $^{13}C/^{12}C$ or $^{15}N/^{14}N$ or $^{17}O/^{16}O$) in Consciousness Energy Treated L-tryptophan was significantly increased by 21.89% compared to the Control sample (Table 1). Thus, the ^{13}C , 2H , ^{15}N , and ^{17}O contributions from $C_{11}H_{13}N_2O_2^+$ to m/z 206 in the Biofield Energy Treated sample was significantly increased compared to the Control sample.

P_M : the relative peak intensity of the parent molecular ion $[M^+]$; P_{M+1} : the relative peak intensity of the isotopic molecular ion $[(M+1)^+]$, M: mass of the parent molecule.

The isotopic abundance ratio of P_{M+1}/P_M ($^2H/^1H$ or $^{13}C/^{12}C$ or $^{15}N/^{14}N$ or $^{17}O/^{16}O$) in the Biofield Energy Treated L-tryptophan was significantly increased compared to the Control sample. The Trivedi Effect[®]-Consciousness Energy Treatment might have the impact on nuclei of L-tryptophan possibly *via* the mediation of neutrino particles would be the solid cause behind the change in the isotopic abundance ratio [15,30,31]. A neutrino is an elementary particle that interacts only *via* the weak subatomic force and gravity. The properties to change identities which are only possible if the neutrinos possess mass and have the ability to interchange their phase from one phase to another internally. Thus, the neutrinos have the ability to interact with protons and neutrons in the nucleus, which indicated a close relation between neutrino and the isotope formation [33, 34]. The altered isotopic composition in molecular level of the Consciousness Energy Treated L-tryptophan might have altered the neutron to proton ratio in the nucleus. The Biofield Energy Treated L-tryptophan with increased stable isotopic abundance ratio, might have changed the physicochemical properties with higher force constant with the atoms of the L-tryptophan. The Biofield Energy Treated L-tryptophan with improved physicochemical properties would be more desirable for the supplements, nutraceutical, and pharmaceutical formulations, which would be advantageous for the prevention and treatment of pellagra, depression, kynurenine. It could also maintain the normal label of tryptophan and avoid increase of its metabolite, lower the neurotoxin and a metabotoxin behavior, glutaric aciduria type I disorder, eosinophilia-myalgia syndrome, incurable and sometimes fatal flu-like neurological condition, etc. Tryptophan is the precursor for the plant hormones like indole alkaloids and auxins. Thus, the Biofield Energy Treated L-tryptophan would be advantageous for the improvement of yield, and productivity of crops.

Conclusions

The Trivedi Effect[®]-Consciousness Energy Treatment showed the significant impact on the isotopic abundance ratio of L-tryptophan. The mass spectra of both the tryptophan samples at retention time 2 minutes exhibited the molecular ion mass peak adduct with hydrogen ion at m/z 205 along with low molecular fragmented mass peaks at m/z 188 and 102 for $C_{11}H_{12}N_2O_2^+$ and $C_8H_6^+$, respectively. The isotopic abundance ratio of P_{M+1}/P_M ($^2H/^1H$ or $^{13}C/^{12}C$ or $^{15}N/^{14}N$ or $^{17}O/^{16}O$) in the Biofield Energy Treated L-tryptophan was significantly increased by 21.89% compared with the Control sample. Therefore, ^{13}C , 2H , ^{15}N , and ^{17}O contributions from $C_{11}H_{13}N_2O_2^+$ to m/z 206.08 in the Biofield Energy Treated tryptophan was increased significantly compared to the Control sample. The change in the isotopic abundance might be

due to the modification in nuclei possibly through the interference of neutrino particles with the help of the 'Trivedi Effect'-Consciousness Energy Treatment. The increased isotopic abundance ratio of the Biofield Energy Treated tryptophan may increase the intra-atomic bond strength, increase its stability, and shelf-life. The Biofield Energy Treated tryptophan might have increased the stability and shelf-life compared to the Control sample. The Treated tryptophan would be more stable in the nutraceutical, and pharmaceutical formulations, which would be advantageous for the prevention and treatment of pellagra, depression, kynurenine. It could also maintain the normal label of tryptophan and avoid increase of its metabolite, lower the neurotoxin and a metabotoxin behavior, eosinophilia-myalgia syndrome, glutaric aciduria type I disorder, incurable and fatal flu-like neurological condition, etc. The Treated L-tryptophan would be advantageous for the improvement of yield, productivity, and quality of crops and other plants.

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